

Tunable Diode Laser Plasmonic Grating Spectroscopy for Hydrogen Sensing

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Abstract—The design and development of portable plasmonic embedded measurement systems represents a significant engineering challenge, aimed at delivering the high sensitivities observed in devices based on such physical phenomena to field applications. This work proposes the Tunable Diode Laser Plasmonic Grating Spectroscopy technique to achieve a system architecture in which narrower resonances observed in metallic diffraction gratings enable the spectral detection of analytes. The primary application investigated is hydrogen sensing using Palladium (Pd) and Niobium (Nb) hydride-forming structures. Analytical and numerical simulations are employed to assess the influence of hydrogen gas presence on the metal dielectric function and structural parameters. It is demonstrated that highly linear detection can be achieved using spectral detection systems, and in the case of a Nb grating on a flexible substrate, a theoretical 55 ppm limit of detection is attainable.

Index Terms—Optical sensors, hydrogen sensors, plasmonics, spectroscopy, Tunable Diode Laser.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE Surface Plasmon Resonance (SPR) effect is typically observed in prism-based coupling schemes [1], [2], and most proposed sensing devices and systems operating based on this effect are configured accordingly [3]. Several portable devices utilizing the Kretschmann configuration have already been reported in the literature, including those designed for both angle-resolved and wavelength-resolved measurements [4], [5]. Notable examples include the *Biacore* [6], developed by the company of the same name and commercialized in 1990, as well as the *SPREETA* [7], developed by Texas Instruments. These devices require precise alignment, and the quality of their measurements is highly dependent on the opto-mechanical system

employed. Moreover, technologies based on this configuration tend to be bulky and challenging to integrate with other systems, as angle-based interrogation requires mechanical rotation of the device for resonant angle measurements, where greater linearity is observed.

Diffraction grating coupling is another configuration that enables the observation of the SPR effect, which can be analyzed in both the angular and spectral domains. This configuration facilitates the narrowing of the resonance curve [8], opening up the possibility of exploring alternative methods for interrogating the SPR effect in gratings through spectral variation, without the need for broadband light sources. This capability is of significant practical importance, as prism-coupled devices face two major impracticalities. The first is the necessity for angular variation of the sample to observe the effect, which becomes problematic in field implementations, particularly when developing portable and/or embedded systems. While broadband sources and spectrometers can be employed to address this issue, these components are bulky and difficult to integrate into practical field measurement systems, limiting their use primarily to laboratory-based demonstrations. Given the resonance narrowing in diffraction gratings, it is worth exploring methods to achieve the required spectral variation for grating resonance observation at a fixed angle—without relying on broadband sources—to develop an interrogation configuration for the SPR phenomenon that overcomes the aforementioned impracticalities [9]. In this context, the Tunable Diode Laser Plasmonic Grating Spectroscopy (TDLPGS) technique is proposed.

This paper presents a system architecture for a practical and portable device that employs a Distributed Feedback (DFB) laser capable of operating under two regimes. First, thermal control is proposed to achieve linear spectral variation, enabling the identification of the most sensitive part of the spectrum. This approach could be employed with gratings in gold (Au) or silver (Ag), materials for which narrower resonances are expected. Additionally, a sinusoidal wavelength modulation scheme is introduced through modulation of the injection current. While thermal control has been previously suggested for fast switching in a communication context [10], to the best of the author's knowledge, its use for interrogating plasmonic devices has not been explored.

The proposed technique is then applied to the sensing of hydrogen gas (H_2) using palladium (Pd) and niobium (Nb) optimized gratings, metals known to form hydrides in the presence of this gas, resulting in optical and structural variations. This

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application is selected due to the critical need for monitoring H_2 in various industries [11], as well as the challenges associated with handling the gas. Hydrogen has a Lower Explosive Limit (LEL) of only 4% volume concentration, being a small molecule with a high risk of leakage, and poses significant safety concerns in its storage and transportation. Additionally, when ignited, its flame is invisible [12], [13]. Another motivation is the exploration of periodicity changes in the grating when the film is exposed to hydrogen, which increases sensitivity.

In contrast with other spectroscopy techniques such as Wavelength Modulation Spectroscopy (WMS) [14], [15], [16] and its variations, such as crystal tuning fork-enhanced spectroscopy [17], [18], [19] and off-axis integrated cavity spectroscopy [20], based on light absorption by the target molecule, the proposed technique in this work consists in the absorption of gas by the grating itself and subsequent interrogation of its plasmonic resonance. Our approach also contrasts with previously suggested H_2 sensors that utilize periodic structures, such as Pd-coated Fiber Bragg Gratings (FBGs), which detect the presence of the gas by measuring the strain caused by hydrogen absorption and its effect on the internal grating periodicity. In this work, the material loaded with the gas serves as the periodic structure, leading to a more direct transducing mechanism [21], [22], [23]. According to the author's knowledge, this is the first detailed analysis of optical and mechanical variations on plasmonic sensing properties of metallic hydrides.

Optimized structures are obtained using the Harmonic Minimization Method (HMM) [24], and the technique is investigated through analytical models that account for gas diffusion in the metals, the dielectric function of the hydride, and the elastic expansion of the films. Numerical simulations are employed to validate the technique and provide calculations of the diffracted fields.

It is shown that a system architecture compatible with a portable, embedded system can achieve high linearity and, depending on the choice of material, a sub-ppm limit of detection.

II. DIFFRACTION GRATING DESIGN AND PHYSICAL ASPECTS OF HYDROGEN ADSORPTION

A. Diffraction Grating Design by Harmonic Minimization Method

To simulate the proposed technique with maximum sensitivity, a design optimization technique should be employed to obtain values for the periodicity and amplitude of the grating that maximize the sensitivity S , defined as the absolute value of the first derivative of the reflectance with respect to wavelength: $S = \left| \frac{dR}{d\lambda} \right|$. In this work, the diffraction gratings are designed in a rectangular shape, as their fabrication is achievable through widely adopted processes such as optical or electron-beam lithography. The optimized structures are obtained using the Harmonic Minimization Method (HMM) with 20 harmonics [24]. This approach allows for the determination of optimal grating parameters by first optimizing a sinusoidal grating using a Rayleigh-based description of its reflectance [25]. From the resulting profile function, a rectangular grating with similar sensitivity is calculated. Since it is possible to obtain good initial

Fig. 1. Wavevector of excited surface plasmon on a diffraction grating.

guesses for both parameters, a gradient-based optimization is employed. For the amplitude, it is known that observing the SPR effect typically requires grating amplitudes on the order of tens of nanometers. Consequently, values between 10 nm and 100 nm are explored, with a resolution of 0.01 nm. For the periodicity, an initial estimation can be derived from the grating equation using the wavevectors illustrated in Fig. 1.

$$k_l = k_x + l \frac{2\pi}{\Lambda}, \quad (1)$$

employing the expression for the surface plasmon wavevector,

$$k_{sp} = k'_{sp} + jk''_{sp}, \quad (2)$$

with [26]

$$k'_{sp} = k_0 \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon' \epsilon_1}{\epsilon' + \epsilon_1}}, \quad (3)$$

$$k''_{sp} = k'_{sp} \frac{\epsilon'' \epsilon_s}{2\epsilon' (\epsilon' + \epsilon_s)}, \quad (4)$$

with $\epsilon_m = \epsilon' - j\epsilon''$ being the metal dielectric function and $\epsilon_s = \eta_s^2$ being the dielectric function of the sensing medium. Then, under normal incidence regime and satisfying the coupling condition $k_l = k_{sp}$, the expression for the grating periodicity initial guess

$$\Lambda \approx \pm l \lambda \left(\frac{\epsilon' \eta_s^2}{\epsilon' + \eta_s^2} \right)^{-1/2}. \quad (5)$$

B. Diffusion of Hydrogen in Metal Gratings

It is important to propose a model for the diffusion of hydrogen in the metallic grating to justify the approach for effective dielectric function calculations and to derive an equation for the response time of the sensing system. Given that the grating amplitude is on the nanometric scale, the diffusion is modeled as diffusion across a planar surface. This simplification is justified by the goal of obtaining an estimation of the sensor response time and the concentration distribution, a thorough analysis of the diffusive behavior over the periodic geometry is beyond the scope of this work. Therefore, by considering an interface between a solution of H_2 in air and a metal at $z = 0$, and applying Fick's second law, the diffusion process can be described.

$$\frac{\partial n(z, t)}{\partial t} = D \frac{\partial^2 n(z, t)}{\partial z^2}, \quad (6)$$

for the conditions

$$\lim_{z \rightarrow \infty} n(z, t) = 0, \quad (7)$$

$$n(z \neq 0, t = 0) = 0, \quad (8)$$

one can obtain the following profile for the gas concentration n

$$n(z, t) = n_0 \exp\left(-\frac{z^2}{4Dt}\right). \quad (9)$$

with n_0 being the fixed concentration on the surface. The response time t_r is then proposed as the time necessary for the optical power to decay by a factor of $\exp(-1)$ at $z = \delta(n, \lambda)$ with $\delta(n, \lambda)$ denoting the concentration-dependent penetration depth

$$\delta(n, \lambda) = \frac{1}{2k_0 \text{Im}[\eta_{ef}(n, \lambda)]}, \quad (10)$$

leading to

$$t_r(n, \lambda) = \frac{1}{16D\{k_0 \text{Im}[\eta_{ef}(n, \lambda)]\}^2}. \quad (11)$$

The equation above is used to calculate the response time for both materials in the concentration range investigated in this work.

C. Effective Dielectric Function Modeling

Considering the diffusive behavior of hydrogen (H) atoms in palladium (Pd) due to gas molecule dissociation, a model for the effective dielectric function must be employed. For this purpose, a specific consideration regarding the concentration distribution in (9) is necessary. The equation predicts a concentration that varies with depth into the metal, meaning that the intruder (H) is not uniformly distributed within the grating. In this work, we adopt the approximation that such variations have a negligible effect on the effective refractive index of the hydride, η_{ef} . This assumption is reasonable in the limit of low gas concentrations, leading to an approach in which the optical properties of the hydride are treated as isotropic.

In light of this argument, two main approaches for modeling η_{ef} are found in the literature: the Bruggeman [27] and Maxwell-Garnett [28] models. The Bruggeman model presents certain limitations, such as symmetry (i.e., switching the host and intruder materials yields the same result), which is undesirable in this case, where the host is a metal. Clearly, if the roles are reversed—making H the host and Pd the intruder—the dielectric function should differ from the original case. Additionally, a comparison between these models for a metallic host and a spherical intruder molecule, both with spherical geometry, has been reported [29]. This comparison demonstrates that the Maxwell-Garnett approach more effectively describes the dielectric function of the composite, as supported by numerical data. Therefore, in this work, the effective dielectric functions of both PdH_n and NbH_n are modeled using the Maxwell-Garnett approximation [30], expressed in terms of the refractive index

Fig. 2. Expansion effect of the hydrogen absorption on the grating structure. On the case of rigid substrate the variation on Λ is non-existent.

of the hydride.

$$\eta_{ef} = \sqrt{n_h^2 + \frac{4\pi\alpha N_a \rho}{1 + (4\pi/3n_h^2)(\alpha N_a \rho)}}, \quad (12)$$

in which the polarizability α can be written as

$$\alpha = R_H^3 n_h^3 \cdot \frac{\eta_i^2 - \eta_h^2}{\eta_i^2 + \eta_h^2}, \quad (13)$$

with R_H as the van der Waals radius of H according to [31], N_a is the number of Avogadro, ρ the concentration of intrusive agents in mol/m^3 , where η_i and η_h are the refractive indexes of the intruder and the host, respectively. To obtain a relation between ρ and the atomic concentration n one can write

$$\rho = n \cdot \frac{N_{mol}^m}{V} = n \cdot \frac{V/V_m^m}{V} = \frac{n}{V_m^m}, \quad (14)$$

with N_{mol}^m being the mole number of metal in the sample, V the volume sample and V_m^m the molar volume of the metal. With these equations, one can calculate the optical effect of hydrogen presence on the metallic grating resonance.

D. Elastic Expansion in Metal Films Under Hydrogen Load

To model the expansion of the grating under hydrogen loading and its effects on the structural parameters, several considerations are necessary. In this work, we assume an elastic model for the metal expansion. It is known that under heavy hydrogen loading, the metal can exhibit plastic deformation; however, for the sake of simplicity, the effect of the plastic region on the grating resonance will be investigated in future works. An important detail of the metal layer behavior is the nature of the substrate. Rigid substrates, such as metals deposited over titanium (Ti) or chromium (Cr) adhesion layers, can suppress the lateral expansion of the film, leaving only the vertical expansion as observable. In the case of a flexible substrate, the film is free to expand laterally, and for a diffraction grating, this results in periodicity variation, which can significantly influence the sensitivity of the final system. It is also expected that, depending on the film thickness, some periodicity variation may occur even with rigid substrates.

With these arguments in mind, two scenarios are explored in this work. The first is a rigid substrate scenario, where no lateral expansion occurs, and the second is an ideally flexible substrate scenario, where the metal grating is free to expand laterally.

Fig. 2 illustrates the vertical and lateral expansions, along with the associated proportional deformations ϵ_z and ϵ_x .

Considering that the proportional deformation associated with isotropic lattice expansion can be written as [32]

$$\epsilon_0 = \frac{\Delta L}{L} = \alpha_H^{Pd/Nb} \cdot n, \quad (15)$$

with $\alpha_H^{Pd/Nb}$ being the expansion factor with its value being adopted from [33] as $\alpha_H^{Pd} = 0.063$ and $\alpha_H^{Nb} = 0.058$. In the case of rigid substrates the expansion associated with ϵ_x is suppressed, but in the case of a flexible substrate one can state that $\epsilon_x = \epsilon_0$. For the case of vertical expansion the contribution of the Poisson effect must be considered and for Pd one can write [32]

$$\epsilon_z^{Pd} = \frac{3C_{44}^{Pd}}{4C_{11}^{Pd} + 8C_{12}^{Pd} + C_{44}^{Pd}} \cdot \epsilon_0 \quad (16)$$

and for Nb [34]

$$\epsilon_z^{Nb} = \left(1 + \frac{C_{11}^{Nb} + 3C_{12}^{Nb} - 2C_{44}^{Nb}}{C_{11}^{Nb} + C_{12}^{Nb} + 2C_{44}^{Nb}} \right) \cdot \epsilon_0 \quad (17)$$

with C_{ij}^{Pd} and C_{ij}^{Nb} being the elastic stiffness of Pd and Nb, respectively, which are obtained from the literature [32], [35], [36]. Using Equations (15) to (17) it is possible to calculate the effect of a gas concentration n on amplitude of the grating as

$$\Delta h = h \cdot \epsilon_z^{Pd/Nb}, \quad (18)$$

and on the grating periodicity as

$$\Delta \Lambda = \lambda \cdot \epsilon_x. \quad (19)$$

III. TUNABLE DIODE LASER PLASMONIC GRATING SPECTROSCOPY TECHNIQUE AND SIMULATOR ALGORITHM

A. Proposed System Architecture

The models proposed in Section II are now employed to validate the Tunable Diode Laser Plasmonic Grating Spectroscopy (TDLPGS) technique proposed in this work. To achieve fixed-angle operation, a setup based on the observation of the fundamental mode of diffraction of the grating under normal incidence is ideal, as this mode exhibits higher sensitivity and narrower resonances. Additionally, the alignment process is simplified under normal incidence conditions. The proposed system architecture is fiber-based, featuring decoupling from the fiber to the sensing medium, reflection at the grating, and recoupling into the fiber, as illustrated in Fig. 3.

The setup incorporates a DFB laser, where both thermal and current variations can be utilized to modulate its emission wavelength. Given that the resonance widths for the materials investigated here are expected to be on the order of 10 nm, it is preferable to modulate the emission wavelength through current variation in a WMS scenario. This approach is complemented by harmonic detection systems such as Fast Fourier Transform (FFT)-based detection and lock-in amplifiers. The beam emitted by the laser is split by a 50/50 coupler, with half of the optical power directed to the system and the other half detected by photodetector PD_1 . The transmitted beam then passes through another optical coupler, where half of the input power is directed

Fig. 3. Proposed TDLPGS system architecture.

to a Gradient Refractive Index (GRIN) lens for efficient coupling and decoupling from the fiber. After decoupling, the beam is reflected by the grating and then coupled back into the fiber, where it is detected by photodetector PD_2 . Each photodetector is paired with a polarizing film to ensure that only the intensities associated with p-polarization are measured. The reflectance is calculated as the ratio of the measured intensities from PD_2 and PD_1 . The reflectance curve is then normalized and analyzed using the FFT and lock-in subsystems.

A practical consideration involves the distance between the tip of the fiber and the grating. It is crucial to ensure that the area associated with the beam diameter is of the same order as the grating area. This consideration is important since there must be several periods of the grating under the illuminance of the beam for diffracted fields to be observable, if the length is several times greater than the beam diameter the surface can reflect as if it was flat. These are considerations that will be important in an experimental implementation of this technique.

B. Simulation Algorithm

To simulate the effect of hydrogen presence on the fundamental mode plasmonic resonance of the grating under normal incidence and to obtain results considering both detection techniques, an algorithm was developed to implement analytical calculations for the effective dielectric function of the metal and the elastic expansion effects on the structural parameters of periodicity and amplitude. The results of optical and mechanical variations for a specific concentration n are then used in a numerical simulation based on the Finite Element Method (FEM) to calculate the fields reflected by the grating. The numerical computation employs a model of a horizontally infinite grating implemented through a Floquet-type periodic boundary condition. The distance from the grating to the emission port is fixed at $10\lambda_i$, where λ_i is the design incident wavelength, and a spectral range from 1520 nm to 1580 nm is used. The mesh is generated

Algorithm 1: Pseudocode for Simulation of TDLPGS.

```

input  $\theta_i, Re(\eta_m), Im(\eta_m), l, \lambda_i, \eta_s, n_{max}$ 
 $[h, \Lambda] \leftarrow$ 
    HHMOptimization[ $\theta_i, Re(\eta_m), Im(\eta_m), l, \lambda_i, \eta_s$ ];
 $n \leftarrow$  LinearVec[ $0, n_{max}$ ];
 $\eta_{ef} \leftarrow$  Eq. (12);
 $\Delta h \leftarrow$  Eq. (19);
if substrate == flexible then
     $\Delta \Lambda \leftarrow$  Eq. (18);
    ELSE  $\Delta \Lambda = 0$ ;
end if
 $t_r \leftarrow$  Eq. (11);
R = CalculateReflectance( $\theta_i, \eta_{ef}, l, \lambda_i, \eta_s, \Delta h, \Delta \Lambda$ );
FFTSignal = FFTanalysis[R];
LockInSignal = LockInAnalysis[R];
Generate plots
    
```

with triangular elements, with the largest and smallest sizes set to 100 nm and 0.2 nm, respectively.

The data obtained from the numerical simulation is then processed by the detection routine, which includes a detection method based on the maximum value of the magnitude of the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT), implemented using the Cooley-Tukey algorithm [37], as well as a digital lock-in amplifier [38], [39] to analyze the signals. It is important to mention that the laser is tuned to have its central wavelength at the point of maximum sensitivity of the curve for $n = 0$, this results in a signal with a weak second harmonic and the detection is focused on the first harmonic of the signal. The overall algorithm used to obtain the results of this work is presented in Algorithm 1.

Initially, the angle of incidence θ_i , the metal refractive index η_m , the diffraction order l , the design wavelength of incidence λ_i , the sensing medium refractive index η_s , and the maximum concentration n_{max} are inputs. The optimal rectangular grating is then obtained, consisting of the pair of structural parameters $[h, \Lambda]$. Subsequently, an equally spaced linear vector n , representing the concentration range to be explored, is created. Equation (12) is employed with n to calculate the refractive index of the hydride η_{ef} , while Equation (19) is used to determine the amplitude variation. In the case of a flexible substrate, Equation (18) is applied to compute the periodicity variation. With this information, the response time t_r is calculated. The numerical model is then employed to compute the reflectance associated with the desired diffraction order. Finally, R is a three-dimensional matrix that stores the reflectance over wavelength for each combination of elements from the η_{ef} , Δh , and $\Delta \Lambda$ vectors.

IV. RESULTS

A. Study of Optical and Mechanical Variations on Plasmonic Resonance

Considering the previously proposed models, each transducing mechanism is initially analyzed separately to understand the effects of dielectric function, amplitude, and periodicity

TABLE I
GRATINGS OBTAINED BY HMM FOR $\lambda_i = 1531$ NM

Material	h (nm)	Λ (nm)
Pd	31.74	1525.64
Nb	34.12	1526.38

Optical constants according to [41] fo Pd and according to [42] for Nb.

TABLE II
OPTICAL AND MECHANICAL VARIATIONS FOR PD GRATING

n	$Re(n_{ef})$	$Im(n_{ef})$	h (nm)	Λ (nm)
0	2.93	8.25	-	-
0.1	8.21	8.42	32.14	1535.25
0.2	10.01	11.50	32.53	1544.86
0.3	9.82	13.57	32.94	1554.47
0.4	9.26	14.69	33.33	1564.09
0.5	8.75	15.30	33.73	1573.70
0.6	8.34	15.65	34.13	1583.31
0.7	8.01	15.87	34.53	1592.92

Fig. 4. Effect of dielectric function variation on Pd grating's resonance curve for different concentrations n .

variations on the sensor response. Subsequently, the combined effects are evaluated for both rigid and ideally flexible substrates.

According to the literature, hydrogen at ambient pressure and temperature forms the hydride PdH_n with an atomic concentration of $n \leq 0.7$ [40]. Therefore, this concentration range will be examined.

For the Pd grating presented in Table I, the effect of optical variations on resonance, as indicated in Table II, is illustrated in Fig. 4.

It can be stated that concentrations below 0.1 have a greater influence on the real part of the effective refractive index, shifting the resonance to significantly lower wavelengths. For higher concentrations, the effect of the imaginary part becomes dominant, with its increase leading to deeper resonances. This result suggests that, even for a non-modulated incident beam, it would be possible to detect low concentrations.

Next, the effect of mechanical variations on resonance is examined. Initially, only the elastic expansion in amplitude is

Fig. 5. Effect of amplitude variation on Pd grating's resonance curve for different concentrations n .

Fig. 7. Effect of gas presence on Pd grating's resonance curve with rigid substrate for different atomic concentrations for different concentrations n .

Fig. 6. Effect of periodicity variation on Pd grating's resonance curve for different concentrations n .

Fig. 8. Effect of gas presence on Pd grating's resonance curve with flexible substrate for different concentrations n .

considered. Fig. 5 presents the results corresponding to the variations outlined in Table II.

From these results, we observe that as the amplitude deviates from the optimized value, higher quality factors are obtained, accompanied by deeper resonances. This mechanism can also contribute to the overall sensitivity of the device.

The variation in periodicity is constrained by the stiffness of the substrate, as previously mentioned. Here, we analyze the effect of this variation by considering an ideally flexible substrate, where the metal film is free to expand laterally. Under this assumption, Fig. 6 presents the results for periodicity expansion alone.

It is evident that the use of flexible substrates can significantly enhance the system's sensitivity, as the resonance position is highly responsive to variations in the grating period. Another possibility is that, even with rigid substrates, some lateral expansion may occur in sufficiently thick films, where the upper part of the grating has some freedom to expand, potentially increasing

sensitivity. The effect of periodicity variation has the potential to dominate the overall sensitivity of the device.

With each transduction mechanism analyzed separately, we can now examine how the device behaves in a scenario more representative of real-world conditions. Considering a rigid substrate, Fig. 7 presents the results of optical and mechanical variations in response to hydrogen concentration, evaluated simultaneously.

For a scenario that involves an ideally flexible substrate, Fig. 8 presents the results for the same concentration range.

In the case of gratings designed with Nb, we analyzed the effects of absorption on the optical constants and structural parameters simultaneously for both substrate types, considering the grating presented in Table I.

To perform the simulation, it is first necessary to determine the atomic concentration at which Nb begins to undergo plastic deformation. Beyond this concentration, the grating will no longer

Fig. 9. Effect of gas presence on Nb grating's resonance curve with rigid substrate for different concentrations n .

Fig. 10. Effect of gas presence on Nb grating's resonance curve with flexible substrate for different concentrations n .

return to its initial dimensions if the concentration decreases. According to the phenomenological model [43], this condition can be expressed as

$$n_{pl}^{Nb} = \frac{1.2}{d} \cdot Ln(5d), \quad (20)$$

for the critical concentration at which plastic deformation begins, as a function of film thickness d , we consider, for example, a 150 nm thick metal film, yielding $n_{pl} = 0.053$. Based on this value, simulations for the Nb device were conducted for $x \leq 0.05$. It is essential to mention that, for both materials, one can expect that the critical hydrogen concentration for plastic deformation increases with the thickness. That means thicker gratings could achieve greater reversibility without compromising sensitivity since this technique is based on the reflected signal under normal incidence. Figs 9

and 10 present the results for rigid and flexible substrates, respectively.

B. Wavelength Modulation Techniques

1) *FFT-Based Detection*: In order to achieve higher sensitivities while maintaining the same system architecture, the sensor is analyzed under sinusoidal wavelength modulation of the employed laser source. Under this condition, the laser current is modulated at 1 kHz, resulting in a beam with a similar modulation frequency in wavelength. This modulation frequency was chosen considering that the spectral feature to be probed is the grating resonance with typical Full-Width-at-Half Maximum (FWHM) on the order of tens of nanometers, which means it is adequate to employ a modulation frequency in a much smaller spectral range. For this reason, the modulation frequency of 1 kHz was chosen to conduct simulations, but it is important to mention that both modulation frequency and amplitude could affect the sensitivity and could be subject of optimization.

For this simulation, a 1 mW optical power beam is used. The detection subsystem consists of a Transimpedance Amplifier (TIA) circuit, incorporating a photodetector with a responsivity of 0.9 A/W, with its current signal mapped to a 0 V–5 V range. Further calculations proceed with a Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) implemented using the Cooley-Tukey algorithm. The final signal considered is the maximum value of the DFT at the modulation frequency. The results for Pd and Nb are presented in Figs. 11 and 12, respectively.

Since the modulated incident beam is expected to enhance sensitivity, the investigated concentration range is reduced by one order of magnitude compared to the previously used range for the rigid substrate and by two orders for the flexible substrate. The results indicate a significant degree of non-linearity for Pd in both substrate cases. For Nb, the rigid substrate scenario exhibited high linearity, which was not observed for flexible substrates.

To minimize the lowest detectable concentration and explore measurement schemes with higher linearity, the signals were analyzed using a computationally implemented digital lock-in technique.

2) *Lock-in-Based Detection*: The lock-in amplifier is an alternative detection scheme that can be implemented for the optical signal under wavelength modulation. This technique is proposed not only due to its well-established success in spectroscopy [44], [45] but also because its digital implementation using embedded electronic devices remains compatible with a portable system architecture.

In this work, lock-in detection is computationally implemented to calculate the magnitude, phase, and both in-phase and quadrature components of the received signal, locked at the modulation frequency. The results for Pd gratings with rigid and flexible substrates are presented in Figs. 13 and 14, respectively. Similarly, the results for Nb gratings are shown in Figs. 15 and 16. The investigated concentration ranges are reduced by one order of magnitude compared to those analyzed using FFT-based detection.

Fig. 11. Result for maximum magnitude of the FFT for both cases of (a) rigid and (b) flexible substrate in Pd grating for different concentrations n .

It is important to make a consideration about the Limit of Detection (LOD) of the proposed scheme to ensure the investigated concentration ranges are above it. To estimate the LOD in terms of minimum detectable reflectance change, one can write

$$LOD = \delta v \cdot \frac{i_{max}}{v_{max} R_e P}, \quad (21)$$

where δv is the resolution of the Analog-to-Digital Converter (ADC) used in the TIA, i_{max} is the maximum photocurrent of the photodiode, v_{max} is the maximum voltage readable by the ADC, R_e is the responsivity of the photodiode, and P is the emitted laser power. Considering a 0 V–5 V range and a 16-bit ADC, we have $\delta v = 0.076$ mV and $v_{max} = 5$ V. For $i_{max} = 0.9$ mA, $R_e = 0.9$ A/W, and $P = 1$ mW, the limit of detection (LOD) is calculated as $1.52 \cdot 10^{-5}$.

Numerical simulations confirm that a reflectance change is observed for a concentration variation of $\delta n = 10^{-3}$ in the Pd grating, yielding $\delta R = 3.1 \cdot 10^{-3}$. For the Nb grating, with $\delta n = 10^{-4}$, the corresponding reflectance change is $\delta R = 2.24 \cdot 10^{-5}$. This indicates that all investigated concentration ranges for

Fig. 12. Result for maximum magnitude of the FFT for both cases of (a) rigid and (b) flexible substrate in Nb grating for different concentrations n .

both structures are above the LOD. Both δR calculations were performed considering incidence at the wavelength of maximum sensitivity.

To facilitate comparisons, it is useful to establish a relation between atomic and volumetric concentrations. For this purpose, the total volume of the hydride can be expressed as

$$V_T = V_m + V_H = N_a^m V_a^m + n N_a^m V_a^H \quad (22)$$

with V_m and V_H being the volumes of metal and hydrogen, respectively, N_a^m the number of metal atoms and V_a^m and V_a^H the atomic volumes of the metal and hydrogen. To obtain the volume percent concentration of hydrogen $c(\%)$ one can write

$$c(\%) = 100 \cdot \frac{V_H}{V_T}, \quad (23)$$

and considering a spheric geometry for each atom one can obtain

$$c(\%) = 100 \cdot \frac{x R_H^3}{R_{Pd}^3 + x R_H^3}. \quad (24)$$

Applying the equation above with $R_{Pd} = 137$ pm [46] and $n = 10^{-3}$ one can obtain $c(\%) = 0.67\%$. For Nb one can employ

Fig. 13. Results for lock-in detection in the case of rigid substrate Pd grating. (a) Magnitude of lock-in signal, (b) Phase, (c) In-phase and (d) Quadrature components for different concentrations n .

Fig. 14. Results for lock-in detection in the case of flexible substrate Pd grating. (a) Magnitude of lock-in signal, (b) Phase, (c) In-phase and (d) Quadrature components for different concentrations n .

Fig. 15. Results for lock-in detection in the case of rigid substrate Nb grating. (a) Magnitude of lock-in signal, (b) Phase, (c) In-phase and (d) Quadrature components for different concentrations n .

Fig. 16. Results for lock-in detection in the case of flexible substrate Nb grating. (a) Magnitude of lock-in signal, (b) Phase, (c) In-phase and (d) Quadrature components for different concentrations n .

Fig. 17. Results for response time. (a) Pd (b) Nb for different concentrations n .

$R_{Nb} = 146$ [46] pm and $n = 10^{-4}$ to obtain $c(\%) = 0.0055\%$. It is important to note that the latter concentration is equivalent to 55 ppm, indicating that this technique employed with the Nb grating could achieve ppm limit of detection.

The saturation of the proposed technique is directly related to the maximum concentration of hydrogen the metal can absorb for a particular temperature and pressure. For ambient temperature and 1 atm pressure, Pd forms the hydride with a concentration of up to $PdH_{0.7}$, for Nb this concentration is around 0.5 [47]. Such values can change according to temperature and pressure, but it requires high pressure (GPa) and high temperature ($10^{2^{\circ}\text{C}}$) to obtain higher concentrations [48]. Since such temperature and pressure ranges are not likely to be observed in practical sensing scenarios, one should not expect that this factor could significantly affect the saturation of the proposed technique.

Another important environmental factor is humidity and its effect on the grating resonance. The air relative humidity can affect the sensing medium refractive index, however, a grating made of metals such as Nb and Pd is insensitive to refractive index variations due to larger resonance widths caused by lower imaginary refractive indexes compared to standard plasmonic

materials such as gold and silver. A humidity-related effect that would provide a significant change to the instrument's response is the dew point. In that case, the formation of droplets of water on the grating surface would require a separate analysis to investigate its effect on the grating resonance.

C. Sensor Response Time

The sensor response time is calculated using (11) for the previously considered concentration ranges. The values for the diffusion coefficient for Pd and Nb are obtained from [49] and [50], respectively. The results are presented in Fig. 17.

It is important to mention that this response time calculation is a "pure" approach, in which the goal is to validate the choice of material and spectral range to be employed in order to achieve better response times but the characteristics of the sensing medium is also very important for the response time since the model considers a fixed concentration on the surface, but in a practical situation the time of gas injection and geometry of the sensing medium is of great importance. These two factors could affect the response time since the flow of the gas and the volume of the considered sensing medium have an impact on the time necessary for the hydrogen concentration to become isotropic within this volume. It is also important to mention that the response time of the photodiodes also add up to the total response time of the measuring system.

V. CONCLUSION

The Tunable Diode Laser Plasmonic Grating Spectroscopy (TDLPGS) technique introduced in this work presents a well-founded system architecture suitable for implementing portable plasmonic measurement systems, applicable in both gaseous and liquid environments. The proposed simulation method, based on homogenization theory for effective dielectric function modeling and the elastic expansion model, is well suited for analyzing the plasmonic properties of hydrogen-absorbing metal sensors.

Simulation results demonstrate that for the system architecture evaluated under wavelength modulation interrogation—through a computational implementation of FFT analysis of the detected optical signal—reasonable linearity was observed in Pd gratings for concentration ranges of $0 \leq n \leq 0.07$ and $0 \leq n \leq 0.007$ for both substrate cases. For Nb-based structures, good linearity was obtained for $0 \leq n \leq 0.005$ under a rigid substrate, but highly non-linear detection was observed for a flexible substrate in the range $0 \leq n \leq 0.0005$.

For Pd structures, detection based on a digital lock-in detection scheme resulted in highly linear detection for all four signal components under a flexible substrate for $0 \leq n \leq 0.007$. For Nb gratings with a rigid substrate, high linearity was also achieved for all four components within the concentration range $0 \leq n \leq 0.005$. For a flexible substrate, good linearity was observed for the magnitude, in-phase, and quadrature components for $0 \leq n \leq 0.0005$. Additionally, it is calculated that for the implementation with Nb diffraction gratings using the lock-in amplifier, the system could achieve a sub-ppm detection limit while maintaining good linearity.

An estimation of the sensor response time is also proposed in order to permit the designer to choose adequate materials and spectral ranges in order to optimize the response time, even though other considerations of experimental nature, such as the design of the gas chamber and velocity of gas flow, would be very important to determine the system final response time.

Future work will include a comprehensive analysis of the effects of plastic deformation under hydrogen loading on plasmonic coupling properties. Furthermore, the experimental implementation of the proposed technique remains a key objective of the research group. Only then can the models suggested here be compared to experimental data, enabling further refinements and developments of the model. The optimization of the modulation frequency will also be investigated.

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